

Pharmacists' attitudes and challenges in implementing the medicines verification system: a pilot study in Bulgaria

Anna Todorova¹

¹ Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Varna, Varna, Bulgaria

² Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Petya Milushewa (p.milusheva@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 15 April 2026 ♦ Accepted 13 May 2026 ♦ Published 12 June 2026

Citation: Todorova A, Kazakova T, Alexandrova J, Milushewa P (2026) Pharmacists' attitudes and challenges in implementing the medicines verification system: a pilot study in Bulgaria. *Pharmacia* 73: e195731. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e195731>

Abstract

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate pharmacists' attitudes toward the medicines verification system and to identify key challenges associated with its implementation in routine pharmacy practice.

Methods: A pilot cross-sectional study was conducted among 257 pharmacists practicing in community and hospital pharmacies in Bulgaria. Data were collected via an anonymous online questionnaire developed and administered through Google Forms. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were performed, including *t*-tests, ANOVA, Mann-Whitney *U*, Kruskal-Wallis tests, and Pearson correlation.

Results: Most respondents reported a low frequency of technical (61.5%) and procedural (63.8%) alerts. However, attitudes toward the system were polarized, with similar proportions expressing positive (42.1%) and negative (43.1%) views. Verification frequency increased by 16.19 percentage points following a regulatory change related to the National Health Insurance Fund. Technical issues, particularly error resolution ($M = 3.74$), were identified as the main barrier. Younger pharmacists and those with less professional experience demonstrated more positive attitudes ($p < 0.001$), while pharmacy managers reported significantly more negative perceptions compared with staff pharmacists ($p = 0.025$).

Conclusion: Although the verification system is functionally integrated and regulatory compliance is high, its acceptance among pharmacists remains influenced by technical reliability, administrative burden, and professional characteristics. Targeted improvements in system performance and workflow integration are essential for enhancing long-term sustainability.

Keywords

Attitudes, Bulgaria, community pharmacy, EMVS, falsified medicines directive, medicines verification system, pharmacists

Introduction

Falsified medicinal products pose a significant threat to public health by potentially containing incorrect or toxic ingredients and failing to meet established standards

of quality, safety, and efficacy (World Health Organization 2017, 2018). The globalization of pharmaceutical markets has further increased the risk of these products infiltrating legal supply chains, necessitating robust systematic control and traceability mechanisms (Mackey

and Nayyar 2017). In response, medicinal product verification has emerged as a critical instrument for ensuring pack-level authenticity. This process involves real-time authentication of a unique 2D Data Matrix code through a centralized system. At the point of dispensing, the pharmacist scans the code to verify it against a national repository; if consistent, the pack is decommissioned to prevent its re-entry into the chain (European Commission 2016; EMVO 2023).

The European Union's legislative framework for this system was established by Directive 2011/62/EU and Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2016/161, which introduced mandatory safety features and verification rules (European Commission 2016; EPCEU 2011). Consequently, the European Medicines Verification System (EMVS) operates via a network of national platforms, including the one implemented in Bulgaria, which connects manufacturers, wholesalers, and pharmacies. Pharmacies are the final safeguard in this model, as they perform the terminal verification before a medicine reaches the patient (Pharmaceutical Group of the European Union 2019). While this role is vital for safe pharmacotherapy, it significantly expands the administrative and organizational workload of pharmacists. Verification occurs via pharmacy software, which generates real-time alerts categorized as either technical (data inconsistencies or software issues) or procedural (discrepancies in pack status, such as re-dispensing attempts) (Bulgarian Drug Agency 2019; Bulgarian Medicines Verification Organisation 2025). The frequency and nature of these alerts serve as primary indicators of the system's functional effectiveness and the practical hurdles faced by end users.

Despite its clear public health objectives, the practical integration of the verification system continues to present significant challenges. Recurrent technical discrepancies, unclear or ambiguous system messages, and extended patient service times directly influence pharmacists' perceptions of the system and contribute to an increased sense of administrative burden (Barrett et al. 2020; Dalton and Byrne 2022). Therefore, the system's ultimate success depends not only on technological infrastructure but also on its seamless acceptance into routine professional practice (Boonstra and Broekhuis 2010).

However, there remains a clear absence of robust empirical evidence concerning the sociotechnical impact of the EMVS on frontline pharmacy practice. Existing literature is largely confined to examinations of regulatory frameworks and technical performance indicators (European Commission 2024a, 2024b), while the limited number of available studies typically focuses on specific national contexts or addresses only the early stages of implementation preparedness (Barrett et al. 2020). Nationally, data on real-world experience and the perceived usefulness of the system in Bulgaria are virtually nonexistent. This study addresses these critical gaps by evaluating pharmacists' attitudes and identifying the key challenges associated with the verification system

in routine practice. This study hypothesizes that, while pharmacists recognize the safety benefits of the system, a high frequency of technical alerts and the resulting administrative burden act as significant barriers to its effective integration.

Materials and methods

Study design

A pilot cross-sectional sociological study was conducted to assess community and hospital pharmacists' attitudes toward the medicines verification system, including their perceptions of its usefulness and effectiveness, the frequency and nature of encountered practical challenges, and its impact on daily workflow and professional practice. The pilot nature of the study aimed to evaluate the applicability of the research instrument and to identify trends that could serve as a basis for a subsequent large-scale national study in Bulgaria.

Study population and participant recruitment

The target population comprised licensed pharmacists (Master of Pharmacy degree holders) practicing in community and hospital pharmacies across Bulgaria. Participants were recruited on a voluntary basis, depending on their willingness to participate. The questionnaire was distributed through direct contact and invitations from the research team, as well as via professional online groups for pharmacists. The survey was open for participation for a period of 37 days (10 July–15 August 2025).

Inclusion criteria

Participants were eligible if they met the following criteria:

- Holding a Master of Pharmacy degree;
- Membership in the Bulgarian Pharmaceutical Union;
- Active practice in a community or hospital pharmacy;
- At least 3 months of practical experience with the medicinal product verification system;
- Voluntary participation.

Exclusion criteria

Participants were excluded if they met any of the following:

- Not actively practicing as pharmacists;
- No direct involvement in dispensing and verification processes;
- Lack of experience with the verification system;
- pharmacy interns;
- Incomplete or inconsistently completed questionnaires.

Data collection instrument

Data were collected via an anonymous online questionnaire developed and administered through Google Forms. The instrument comprised 17 items, including 14 closed-ended and three open-ended questions, and was designed by the research team based on an extensive literature review and the specific operational characteristics of the Bulgarian medicines verification system. To ensure the clarity and comprehensibility of the items, a pilot test was conducted among a small group of pharmacists ($n = 10$), with no significant difficulties or ambiguities reported. The questionnaire was organized into two primary thematic sections. The first section gathered demographic and professional characteristics, including age, gender, regional pharmaceutical chamber; years of professional experience; type of pharmacy; and professional position. The second section focused on attitudes and practical aspects of the verification process, assessing the frequency of verification and the nature of alerts encountered. Additionally, this section used a 5-point Likert scale to evaluate the perceived level of difficulty, alongside items exploring participants' opinions on the necessity and effectiveness of the system and their prior experience with falsified medicinal products.

Sample size

A total of 289 questionnaires were received by the end of the data collection period. Following a rigorous validation process, 257 (88.9%) were deemed valid and included in the final analysis. Thirty-two questionnaires were excluded due to incomplete entries, logical inconsistencies, or missing data on key variables.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using both descriptive and inferential methods. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, expressing categorical variables as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were presented as means with standard deviations (SD). Prior to inferential testing, data were assessed for normality and homogeneity of variances using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene's tests, respectively.

For group comparisons, parametric tests, including the independent-samples *t*-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), were employed for normally distributed data. In cases where the assumption of equal variances was violated during ANOVA, the Games–Howell *post hoc* test was applied for multiple comparisons. For data that did not meet the assumptions for parametric analysis, non-parametric alternatives, such as the Mann–Whitney *U* and Kruskal–Wallis tests, were used. The relationship between continuous variables was evaluated using the Pearson correlation coefficient. All statistical tests were two-tailed, and a *p*-value of < 0.05 was considered the threshold for statistical significance. Statistical analyses

were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows Version 19.0 software.

Ethical considerations

The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Varna (Protocol No. 17/03.07.2025).

Results

The study included a total of 257 Master of Pharmacy practitioners from various regions across the country. The demographic and professional characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic and professional characteristics of respondents ($N = 257$).

Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	195	75.9
Male	62	24.1
Regional pharmaceutical chamber		
Sofia	140	54.5
Varna	38	14.8
Ruse	20	7.8
Plovdiv	10	3.9
Other	49	19.1
Age group		
≤ 30 years	84	32.7
31–40 years	48	18.7
41–50 years	57	22.2
51–60 years	55	21.4
≥ 61 years	13	5.1
Years of professional experience		
< 5 years	68	26.5
5–10 years	40	15.6
11–20 years	54	21.0
> 20 years	95	37.0
Type of pharmacy		
Community pharmacy	225	87.5
Hospital pharmacy	32	12.5
Professional position		
Pharmacist	161	62.6
Pharmacy manager	96	37.4

Most respondents were female (75.9%), with the largest proportion falling into the under-30 age group (32.7%). Geographically, more than half of the participants were affiliated with the Sofia Regional Pharmaceutical Chamber (54.5%). Regarding professional experience, the distribution showed a notable bimodal trend: 37.0% of pharmacists had more than 20 years of practice, while 26.5% had less than 5 years. Most respondents were employed in community pharmacies (87.5%), with 62.6% practicing as staff pharmacists and 37.4% serving as pharmacy managers.

The survey further explored pharmacists' perceptions regarding the frequency of technical and procedural alerts during the verification process, routine verification practices, and general attitudes toward the system. Additionally, the study assessed participants' real-world experience with falsified medicinal products encountered within the legal supply chain. The summarized results of these findings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Occurrence of alerts, verification frequency, experience, and pharmacists' perceptions ($N = 257$).

Indicator Category	<i>n</i>	%
Frequency of technical alerts		
Very rarely (\leq once per week)	158	61.5
Rarely ($<$ 5 times per day)	68	26.5
Frequently (\leq 10 times per day)	28	10.9
Very frequently ($>$ 10 times per day)	3	1.2
Frequency of procedural alerts		
Very rarely (\leq once per week)	164	63.8
Rarely ($<$ 5 times per day)	70	27.2
Frequently (\leq 10 times per day)	18	7.0
Very frequently ($>$ 10 times per day)	5	1.9
Verification frequency (OTC/non-reimbursed medicines)		
Only packs without a linear barcode	17	6.6
Rarely ($<$ 50% of packs)	24	9.3
Frequently ($>$ 50% of packs)	38	14.8
Always/almost always ($>$ 90% of packs)	178	69.3
Verification after regulatory change (NHIF)		
Did not work in a pharmacy before the change	36	14.0
Rarely ($<$ 50% of packs)	91	35.4
Frequently ($>$ 50% of packs)	38	14.8
Always/almost always ($>$ 90% of packs)	92	35.8
Attitudes towards the necessity of the verification system		
Strongly agree	41	16.0
Rather agree	67	26.1
No opinion	38	14.8
Rather disagree	51	19.8
Strongly disagree	60	23.3
Experience with falsified medicinal products		
Yes	9	3.5
No	228	88.7
Yes, but not detected through the verification system	20	7.8

Most respondents reported encountering system alerts infrequently, with 61.5% noting that technical alerts and 63.8% noting that procedural alerts occurred "very rarely" in daily practice. Nevertheless, 69.3% of surveyed pharmacists consistently carried out routine verification of over-the-counter (OTC) medicinal products, despite the system's technical demands.

Regarding general attitudes toward the necessity of the verification system, the study found a polarized distribution: 43.2% ($n = 111$) of participants expressed a predominantly negative attitude, while 42.0% ($n = 108$) held a predominantly positive view. Furthermore, most respondents (88.7%) reported that they had never encountered falsified medicinal products during their professional practice.

To evaluate the impact of the regulatory change mandated on 2 January 2024, which made verification compulsory for National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF)-reimbursed prescription medicines, a comparative analysis was conducted. This analysis assessed the reported verification frequency before and after the implementation of the NHIF-related requirements. The comparison of the mean verification frequencies for these two periods is detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparative analysis of the mean verification frequency before and after the NHIF-related regulatory change ($N = 257$).

Period	Minimum (%)	Maximum (%)	Mean (%)
Before NHIF-related change	48.54	77.11	62.83
After NHIF-related change	70.62	87.42	79.02

Difference (Δ) in mean verification frequency: +16.19 percentage points.

A significant increase in verification activity was observed following the regulatory change. For the study period (July–August 2025), the verification frequency ranged from 70.62% to 87.42%, with a mean frequency of 79.02%. In contrast, prior to 2 January 2024, the frequency ranged from 48.54% to 77.11%, with a notably lower mean of 62.83%. This represents a substantial absolute increase of 16.19 percentage points in the mean verification frequency, underscoring a substantial intensification of system utilization directly linked to the NHIF-related mandate.

To identify the primary barriers to the verification process, respondents ranked various factors according to their perceived impact using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 represents the least impact and 5 represents the greatest. These results, which categorize the challenges hindering routine pharmacy practice, are presented in Table 4.

The analysis of barriers to the verification process (Table 4) revealed that resolving technical errors was perceived as the most significant challenge (mean, $M = 3.74$), with more than half of the respondents (56.4%) ranking it as a high-impact difficulty. In contrast, other factors—such as scanning procedures, nomenclature updates, and maintenance costs—received lower mean scores, ranging from 2.82 to 2.94. Approximately one-third of the participants perceived these latter factors as substantial hurdles in their daily routine.

In the final section of the questionnaire, 19.46% ($n = 50$) of the participants provided additional qualitative feedback via an open-ended comment field. These responses were categorized based on the nature of the opinions expressed and the specific problems described. For respondents who addressed multiple issues, each distinct point was coded and recorded separately for the thematic analysis presented in Table 5.

The thematic analysis of the open-ended comments (Table 5) revealed a predominance of negative and critical perspectives toward the verification system. The most frequently cited issues included a generalized negative attitude (5.1%), followed by organizational and technical hurdles, such as delays in the dispensing process (4.3%) and specific software-related technical problems (3.9%). Critical views regarding the overall effectiveness of the

Table 4. Assessment of factors hindering the verification process.

Factor	Low impact (1–2) %	Moderate impact (3) %	High impact (4–5) %	Mean ± SD
Scanning is time-consuming	44.0	21.8	34.2	2.88
Resolving technical errors is time-consuming	21.0	22.6	56.4	3.74
System maintenance is costly for the pharmacy	45.1	23.3	31.5	2.82
Updating the product nomenclature is time-consuming	42.8	21.0	36.2	2.94

Note: 1–2 = low impact; 3 = moderate impact; 4–5 = high impact.

Likert scale: 1 (very low) to 5 (very high).

Table 5. Thematic analysis of respondents' comments on the verification system.

Theme	n	%
Negative aspects		
Overall negative opinion	13	5.1
Organizational issues		
Delays in dispensing	11	4.3
Incomplete implementation due to insufficient stakeholder requirements	1	0.4
Technical issues		
Reported specific technical difficulties	10	3.9
Unsatisfactory overall technical performance	3	1.2
Critical views on effectiveness		
Falsification occurs predominantly in other supply channels	6	2.3
Positive effects		
Prevention of dispensing errors	3	1.2

system were also noted, while isolated positive comments highlighted its potential in preventing medication errors. Collectively, these qualitative findings underscore a dominant perception of the system as a source of practical difficulty in routine pharmacy practice.

Based on the survey results, further statistical analyses were conducted to identify potential differences in attitudes toward verification across various demographic and professional subgroups. These included comparisons based on gender, age, years of professional experience, pharmacy type (community vs. hospital), and professional position (pharmacy manager vs. staff pharmacist). A comprehensive summary of these statistical tests and their significance is provided in Table 6.

The results indicate that no statistically significant difference in attitudes toward the verification system was observed based on gender ($U = 5819.5$; $p = 0.561$), with similar mean ranks reported for females (MR = 130.50) and males (MR = 124.37). Likewise, no significant difference was identified according to the type of pharmacy ($t = -1.875$; $p = 0.062$), although pharmacists working in hospital phar-

macies demonstrated higher mean scores ($M = 2.34$) compared with those in community pharmacies ($M = 1.84$).

A weak but statistically significant negative correlation was found between age and attitudes ($r = -0.216$; $p < 0.001$), indicating a tendency toward less positive attitudes with increasing age. Years of professional experience were also significantly associated with attitudes ($F = 8.053$; $p < 0.001$), with pharmacists having up to 5 years of experience demonstrating the most positive attitudes ($M = 2.57$) compared with those with longer professional tenures.

A statistically significant difference was also observed according to professional position ($t = 2.336$; $p = 0.025$). Staff pharmacists reported more positive attitudes ($M = 2.06$) than pharmacy managers ($M = 1.64$). In contrast to attitudes, no significant differences were found in reported real-world experience with falsified medicinal products based on either position ($U = 7657.0$; $p = 0.820$) or years of experience ($\chi^2 = 1.267$; $p = 0.737$).

In summary, professional experience and professional role within the pharmacy appear to be key factors associated with differences in attitudes toward the medicines verification system.

Discussion

The present study demonstrates that, although more than 60% of pharmacists report that technical and procedural alerts rarely occur in routine practice, attitudes toward the verification system remain sharply divided. Comparable proportions of respondents expressed positive (42.1%) and negative (43.1%) views, suggesting a discrepancy between regulatory requirements and the perceived value of the system in everyday practice. Similar polarized attitudes have been reported in international studies, where pharmacists acknowledge the importance of verification for ensuring medicine safety, while simultaneously perceiving it as an additional administrative burden (Barrett et al. 2020; Dalton

Table 6. Associations between sociodemographic factors and attitudes toward the verification system.

Variable	Test	Key result	Statistic	p-value
Gender	Mann-Whitney <i>U</i>	Women: MR = 130.50; Men: MR = 124.37	$U = 5819.5$	0.561
Age	Pearson correlation	Weak negative correlation	$r = -0.216$	< 0.001
Years of experience	Welch ANOVA	≤ 5 years group showed higher mean scores compared to other groups	$F = 8.053$	< 0.001
Type of pharmacy	Independent <i>t</i> -test	Community: $M = 1.84$; Hospital: $M = 2.34$	$t = -1.875$	0.062
Position	Independent <i>t</i> -test	Pharmacists: $M = 2.06$; Managers: $M = 1.64$	$t = 2.336$	0.025
Position - counterfeit experience	Mann-Whitney <i>U</i>	MR = 129.44 vs 128.26	$U = 7657.0$	0.820
Experience - counterfeit cases	Kruskal-Wallis	No significant differences	$\chi^2 = 1.267$	0.737

and Byrne 2022). The findings of the present study align with evidence reported across multiple European Union member states, including Italy, Poland, Germany, and Spain. In these countries, the implementation of the European Medicines Verification System (EMVS) has similarly been associated with a range of operational and perceptual challenges. In Italy, the long-established national medicines traceability framework (Bollino system), which predates the Falsified Medicines Directive, has supported a relatively smooth technical transition to the newer verification requirements. Nonetheless, existing studies indicate that pharmacists continue to experience increased workload and perceive limited added value from the additional verification layer (Mackey and Nayyar 2017; European Commission 2023). In Poland, as in other Central and Eastern European countries, the early phases of implementation have been marked by challenges related to system interoperability, alert management, and the need for additional staff training. These issues have collectively reduced workflow efficiency and hindered user acceptance (Melia et al. 2024). Similar patterns have been reported in Germany and Spain, where high levels of compliance are primarily driven by regulatory obligations rather than strong professional endorsement of the system (European Commission 2023). These observations closely mirror the findings of the present study, where attitudes remain polarized despite relatively low frequencies of technical and procedural alerts. Evidence from additional EU settings indicates that pharmacists widely recognize the safety benefits of the system. At the same time, however, they frequently perceive it as an additional administrative burden that affects routine practice (Barrett et al. 2020; Dalton and Byrne 2022). Overall, the convergence of findings across multiple European countries indicates that the challenges observed in Bulgaria are not isolated but instead reflect broader sociotechnical barriers inherent to the large-scale implementation of digital medicines verification systems within pharmacy practice.

The observed increase in the mean verification frequency by +16.19 percentage points following the regulatory change associated with the NHIF indicates that regulatory mechanisms have a direct impact on professional behavior. This finding aligns with previous analyses by both the European Commission and the European Medicines Verification Organisation (EMVO), which highlight that the mandatory nature of verification is a key driver of high compliance levels within the system (European Commission 2016; EMVO 2023). At the same time, the increased intensity of verification activities may contribute to a higher perceived workload, particularly when technical issues are identified as the most significant barrier ($M = 3.74$).

The finding that resolving technical errors is perceived as the most substantial challenge is in line with the literature on the implementation of digital health systems, where technical difficulties and integration issues are among the primary barriers to adoption by healthcare professionals (Boonstra and Broekhuis 2010). This underscores that the system's technological reliability plays a pivotal role in shaping pharmacists' trust. Notably, younger pharma-

cists and those with fewer years of professional experience demonstrate more positive attitudes toward the system ($r = -0.216$; $p < 0.001$; $F = 8.053$; $p < 0.001$). This relationship can be understood as reflecting the stronger digital adaptability and greater openness to adopting new technological tools typically seen among younger professionals—a phenomenon widely described in studies on digitalization in healthcare (Venkatesh et al. 2003; Gagnon et al. 2016).

In contrast, pharmacy managers exhibit more negative attitudes compared with staff pharmacists ($p = 0.025$), which may be explained by the broader administrative responsibilities associated with managerial roles. These responsibilities include ensuring system functionality at the pharmacy level, maintaining barcode scanning equipment, managing subscription costs, monitoring system performance across workstations, supporting staff in resolving technical issues, and overseeing software updates.

The limited real-world experience with falsified medicinal products—reported by 88.7% of pharmacists as absent in their practice—may contribute to a lower perceived individual benefit of the system. At the European level, cases of falsified medicines entering the legal pharmacy supply chain are considered rare, which may create a mismatch between perceived risk and the administrative effort required (EMVO 2023).

In summary, the findings suggest that while the verification system functions effectively from a regulatory perspective, its professional acceptance remains influenced by technical reliability, organizational burden, and individual characteristics of pharmacists. Improvements in system performance and workflow integration may enhance professional acceptance and contribute to the long-term sustainability of the system.

Study limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. The use of a non-random sampling approach limits the representativeness of the sample and the generalizability of the findings. The pilot design implies a relatively limited scope and necessitates confirmation through larger-scale studies. In addition, the data are based on self-reported responses, which may introduce subjective bias. Finally, the lack of comparable national studies further limits the ability to contextualize and benchmark the findings.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that the medicines verification system is functionally integrated into pharmacy practice, with most pharmacists reporting a low frequency of technical and procedural alerts alongside high compliance rates. The regulatory shift associated with the NHIF mandate has led to a significant increase in verification frequency, confirming the effectiveness of legislative mechanisms in ensuring system adherence.

However, attitudes toward the system remain polarized. Technical difficulties, particularly those related to error resolution, are perceived as the primary barrier to seamless integration. The more positive outlook observed among younger pharmacists suggests a higher degree of digital adaptability, indicating significant potential for the sustainable integration of digital health tools in future pharmacy practice.

The findings underscore the need for further optimization of the technical infrastructure and enhanced communication strategies. Targeted training on the tangible benefits of the system is essential to address the negative perceptions held by pharmacy managers and senior pharmacists. Such efforts are essential for strengthening professional acceptance and supporting the system's long-term sustainability.

As a pilot study, these results underscore the necessity for larger-scale, nationally representative research in Bulgaria to validate these trends and allow for a more granular analysis of the factors influencing system perception. Furthermore, future research incorporating objective transactional data from the verification system and cross-country comparative analyses would provide a more comprehensive evaluation of its functionality and impact on global pharmaceutical practice.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

The study was financed with funds from the state budget, provided through the Ministry of Education and Science (MES) to the Science Fund at the Medical University of Varna for financing the scientific activity inherent in state higher education institutions under project No. 24009.

Author contributions

All authors contributed equally to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection, and analysis were performed by J.A., T.K., A.T., and P.M. The first draft of the manuscript was written by A.T., and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Anna Todorova <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9273-3487>

Petya Milushewa <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6606-5048>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary material 1: table S1

Authors: Anna Todorova, Tanya Kazakova, Joanna Alexandrova, Petya Milushewa

Data type: zip

Explanation note: Original Bulgarian version of the survey on pharmacists' attitudes towards verification.

Copyright notice: This dataset is made available under the Open Database License (<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0>). The Open Database License (ODbL) is a license agreement intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Dataset while maintaining this same freedom for others, provided that the original source and author(s) are credited.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e195731.suppl1>